

Director's Perspective

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This second issue of *The Mirror* marks the end of the first year of the full NOIRLab—the unification of NSF's night-time optical/infrared astronomy facilities in a single organization. It has not been quite the year that we planned, but we are not alone in our experience—people around the world, and all of our readers, are wrestling with the same challenges we face.

This edition of *The Mirror* reminds us that the scientific community is still going strong, people still have many clever ideas and great science is still being done with our facilities, with new data, and with data that has had time to mature.

One of society's challenges, and a key part of our mission, is ensuring that the *best ideas* are recognized irrespective of the particulars of the person or persons who generate them. In the *Perspectives* section of this issue, two scientists share their thoughts on how we can improve our proposal review process and participation in science from people of all walks and all institutions. Their observations and recommendations are based on *data*—on methods tested at other institutions and on the power of big data to level the playing field and empower people. We are building our next generation of tools and processes with these ideas in mind, but there is more that we can, and will, do. This issue also responds to our community's interest in learning more about where their data come from: Jacelle Ramon-Sauberger shares information about the Tohono O'odham Nation, where Kitt Peak National Observatory is located.

The breadth of the science highlights in this issue is impressive. They range from uncovering the population of short gamma ray bursts at high redshifts, to observing recoiling

black holes, to the discovery of low mass dwarf stars in our own solar neighborhood, to searches for asteroids tidally captured by Venus. These ideas are backed by equally clever technology—both hardware and software—and the power of public engagement in scientific research. Adaptive optics enables dissection of dense star clusters while visible-light speckle interferometry allows our telescopes to capture images with resolution rivaling that of the Hubble Space Telescope. Some of the science detailed here requires deep exposures with our largest apertures, others use our smallest telescopes—and pass the light through a diffuser to allow ultra-precise measurement. Sophisticated software turns the record of photon arrival times and angles ultimately into images with brightness, color, and motion.

The hardware and software do not come from thin air—talented and dedicated people create, maintain, and operate them knowing that they too are a vital part of a larger scientific enterprise. As we work from home it is harder to experience that sense of community between the observatories and our users, but this issue of *The Mirror* shows that it is still strong. As we return to the mountain tops and laboratories, we feel a sense of reconnecting with our world, with our peers, with the sky. During this period of remote working, our team has kept in close contact with the scientific users of our facilities, with students and educators adapting to the new and challenging circumstances, and with astronomy enthusiasts around the world. Good evidence of this are the ongoing citizen science projects that harness the public's fascination with astronomy to drive important discoveries. The exciting science illustrated in *The Mirror* shows that while many of us are working remotely, we are still working *together* to advance our understanding of the Universe.